

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ELECTION SYSTEM IN INCREASING THE INFLUENCE OF POLITICAL PARTIES IN SOCIETY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

The globalization of political processes in the modern world further strengthens the connection between the activities of political parties and electoral systems. The electoral system is one of the main factors contributing to increasing the influence of political parties in society. Also, the presence of the direct impact of political parties on improving the democratic nature of elections is of great importance, and today it is one of the urgent topics in the research center of modern political science.

In Uzbekistan, practical reforms to strengthen the participation of political parties in political processes have also accelerated in recent years. In particular, measures to improve the electoral system have been strengthened to enhance the influence of political parties in society.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, political party, electoral system, democracy, civil society, majoritarian electoral system, proportional electoral system, mixed electoral system, electorate.

Introduction. In global academia, extensive research has been conducted on the relationship between party systems and electoral systems, which are crucial components of the political system. While there are numerous approaches to the formation and development of political party institutions and electoral institutions, the majority of political scientists are unanimous in their opinion regarding the connection between them, emphasizing that "there is a strong correlation". Speaking about elections, we can observe that in the context of today's globalization, with the expansion of the geography of democracy, the transparency and democratic nature of elections are increasing, and the possibilities of using modern internet technologies during the election campaign are growing year by year. From this point of view, in Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the further democratization of elections, ensuring the free participation and competition of political parties. Especially significant is the fact

that the last elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and local Kengashes, held on October 27, 2024, were held based on the "Mixed" electoral system for the Legislative Chamber, aimed at further increasing the influence of political parties in society.

Main Part. When discussing electoral systems and their impact on the activities of political parties, we must first pay attention to their connection with the political system and political regime. In political science, the political system is considered a broad concept, and we can cite the political regime, party system, and electoral systems as its integral components. The characteristics of the political system are determined by the political regime, which is its main component. That is, whether a political regime is authoritarian or democratic is reflected in the characteristics of the political system. Institutions operating in society can also be characterized by their authoritarian or democratic nature, depending on the type of political regime.

The electoral system and the party system are also characterized in direct connection with the type of political regime. For example, in a democratic regime, as a rule, a multi-party system operates, and the electoral system is fair and transparent.

To establish democratic elections, it is first of all necessary that the legislative framework comply with generally recognized international electoral standards. In general, regarding the concept and essence of "international electoral standards," it should be noted that "international electoral standards are understood as the principles of international law on the organization and conduct of elections related to the electoral rights of citizens"[2]. For the electoral system of each country to be democratic, it is necessary, first of all, to comply with "International Electoral Standards".

In Uzbekistan, democratic elections are also held within the framework of a multi-party system. Electoral systems are divided into three types. 1. Majoritarian electoral system. 2. Proportional electoral system. 3. Mixed electoral system. Let us briefly dwell on the above-mentioned electoral systems.

The electoral system is a political institution related to the organization of the process of electing politicians, the implementation of voting procedures, and the determination of results, as well as the distribution of mandates (legal relations of representation, vacant seats occupied through elections) between parties[5] many scholars describe the electoral system in connection with political parties.

A majoritarian electoral system (from the French word "majorité," meaning majority) is understood in constitutional law as determining the outcome of voting in elections to representative bodies.

A positive aspect of the majoritarian electoral system is that voters pay attention directly to the candidate's personality, get acquainted with him, communicate with him, and have clear control over his activities. In elections held under a majoritarian system, the number of votes cast for the winning candidate or the winning party is mainly a minority, and most regrettably, the remaining votes are not counted.

The proportional electoral system (Latin *proportio* - proportion) is one of the types of electoral systems that emerged a century after the majoritarian electoral system.

Positive aspects of the proportional electoral system:

- the votes of voters constituting a minority are also taken into account, and the political parties that received votes in it also occupy seats in parliament;
- With its help, it is possible to see real and accurate pictures of the location of political forces in the political life of society;
- ensures the development of pluralism of opinions and a multi-party system, as well as close interaction between the state and citizens;
- a proportional representation system allows each political party to receive several seats proportional to the number of votes. Therefore, this system creates more just conditions for political parties than the majoritarian system;
- voters vote not for candidates with a higher chance of being elected, but for the party they believe in based on the programs of political parties;
- allows voters to choose a political party and thereby reduces the influence of parties on the composition of their representatives in parliament [1].

The mixed electoral system is essentially a combination of two systems: proportional and majoritarian. In this case, one part of the mandates is distributed according to the proportional system (by party lists), and the other part - according to the majoritarian system (voting for a candidate). This electoral system is one of the manifestations of the electoral system, reflecting the combination of proportional and majoritarian electoral systems in several countries.

Different electoral systems can contribute to the development of different party organizations and party systems (two-party or multi-party); contribute to the formation of party electoral blocs; and contribute to the formation of a single-party or coalition government [3]. The party system operating in the

political system and the electoral system play an important role in shaping each other and demonstrating its specific characteristics. For example, in a proportional electoral system, an increase in the role of political parties in society is observed. To be clearer, in a proportional electoral system, voters vote for political parties, which form their representatives based on a list.

In Uzbekistan, the elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan and local councils held on October 27, 2024, were also held at a high level, based on democratic principles. The elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan were held based on a new mixed electoral system.

The mixed electoral system currently operates in such countries as Germany, Spain, Japan, Hungary, Australia, New Zealand, Guinea, Albania, South Korea, Lithuania, Somalia, Mexico, and Taiwan (PRC), and within the CIS - in Russia, Armenia, Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, Georgia - a total of about 40 countries.

For example, in Australia, one chamber of parliament is elected according to the majoritarian system, and the other according to the proportional system. In Egypt, the mixed system consists of a combination of party list voting and individual elections: one individual candidate is elected in each electoral district, and the remaining seats are distributed among those on the party list. In the Mexican United States, the House of Representatives of the Federal Congress consists of 300 deputies elected under a majoritarian system and 100 deputies elected under a proportional representation system[4].

In conclusion, it should be noted that the elections to the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan and local councils held in Uzbekistan on October 27, 2024, were held based on the "Mixed Election" system for the Legislative Chamber, which is directly aimed at increasing the influence of political parties in society. As we have seen, in a proportional electoral system, voting directly through in-depth familiarization with the pre-election programs put forward by political parties increases voters' interest in closely familiarizing themselves with their activities. This, in turn, will further clarify the electorate of political parties and serve to ensure healthy competition between them.

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